

Coming in 2021: The First Rubin Observatory Data Preview

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Vera C. Rubin Observatory will soon begin the Legacy Survey of Space and Time (LSST), providing the scientific community with an unprecedented amount of astronomical data. Progress on Rubin's data infrastructure and pre-operations planning has continued on schedule, despite the COVID-19 pandemic, and the Rubin Observatory Operations team is pleased to announce a series of three "data previews" in advance of the start of the LSST. Work on the first Data Preview (DP0) will continue throughout FY21.

The three data previews will provide opportunities for the Rubin Operations team to rehearse and refine the data release process—which will occur annually during the LSST—before the survey begins. Just as importantly, the data previews will help members of the science community familiarize themselves with the tools and the analysis techniques they will need to do science with LSST data. Lessons learned from each data preview will ensure that everyone is as ready as possible when operations begin. *"This will definitely be a work in progress,"* notes Amanda Bauer, Deputy Director of Operations for Rubin Observatory, *"with plenty of opportunity for input along the way."*

Although the Operations team's goal is to make the three data previews resemble, as much as possible, the data releases that will occur during Rubin Operations, it's important to note that the preview data will be very different from the survey data. DP0 will use a simulated dataset intended to look very much like Rubin data, in the sense that the images will resemble full-frame LSST Camera images, and the catalog products will feature the kinds of measurements that will be made using the science pipelines during the survey. The second and third data previews (DP1 and DP2) will feature commissioning data. The primary objective when gathering data during the commissioning phase is to test every aspect of the Rubin Observatory system, so although the observations will be on-sky, commissioning data won't really start to resemble LSST data until the very end of the commissioning phase—and even then it will mostly have different (in many cases higher) temporal sampling from the survey data.

The simulated dataset that will be used in DP0 was built by the Rubin Observatory LSST Dark Energy Science Collaboration (DESC) and is referred to as DC2. The Rubin Operations team has partnered with DESC to provide this dataset for DP0 because it will allow the science community to experience the true scale of LSST data. *"DP0 is designed to get people thinking about how to handle the LSST data,"* points out Phil Marshall, Deputy Director for Rubin Observatory Operations at SLAC National Accelerator Laboratory (SLAC), *"so even if the data aren't exactly what they want for their science, they will get them started working with the kinds of tools that will help them make the best use of subsequent data previews—and eventually, the survey data."*

In the fall of 2020, the Rubin Operations team established a cloud-based Interim Data Facility (IDF) to host Rubin preview data and support pre-operations activities while a permanent US Data Facility is selected. Now, multiple efforts are proceeding simultaneously in preparation for DP0. The DC2 dataset is being ingested by the IDF, and the Rubin Data Management construction team is preparing the science pipelines to process the data and refining the tools the science community will use to access it (all deployed by the Operations team at the IDF). Meanwhile, the newly formed Rubin Observatory Community Engagement Team (CET) is working with scientists and building an online collaborative community and coordinating the development of scientific documentation and tutorials. The CET is part of the Rubin Operations System Performance department; these efforts start during the pre-operations data previews and will continue into Rubin Operations. The CET is committed to facilitating equitable access to LSST data and services, in order to enable scientific excellence from our broad and diverse user community. *"The groundbreaking scientific potential of the LSST dataset requires a proportionally innovative and progressive community engagement model,"* says Melissa Graham, the Lead Community Scientist for Rubin Observatory. *"DP0 is the first in a series of steps towards operations, and the CET is looking forward to working with the community to build an effective model for scientific engagement."*

A visual representation of the Rubin Science Platform in use with a background image of the spiral galaxy IC342. Credit: Rubin Obs/KPNO/NOIRLab/NSF/AURA/H. Schweiker (WIYN/NOIRLab)/T. A. Rector (University of Alaska Anchorage)

During the LSST, Rubin Observatory data will be available to all scientists with data rights, but DP0 must be deployed with a subset of the science community to prevent overloading the IDF and other data infrastructure still in development. The community members selected for DP0 will broadly represent the Rubin community, including those identified as experienced users, inexperienced users, members of the Science Collaborations, Chilean colleagues, and scientists and educators from small and underserved institutions. As the data previews progress, support for community participation will increase until (at least by the start of operations) all data rights holders are able to engage with the commissioning data. The process for selecting science community members to participate in DP0 will be announced in early 2021. As there will be two stages of DP0—as first the original DESC simulated dataset is made available to users (2021), and then later after this dataset is

reprocessed by the Rubin science pipelines in order to more closely mimic an LSST data release (2022)—there will be multiple opportunities for participation. The CET is currently preparing resources to support DP0 community participants and help them learn about the simulated data products and how to access them in the IDF.

The Operations team anticipates that the data previews will improve with each iteration, as the Rubin Observatory Data Management team continues to develop the data infrastructure, and as community feedback is incorporated. “We’re as eager to provide Rubin Observatory data to the science community as they are to receive them,” says Bob Blum, Rubin Observatory Acting Operations Director. “We expect the data previews to be exciting—and a learning process—for everyone involved.”